

STUDY OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARD GPP AND IMPLEMENTATION ACTUALITY

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Abstract. *Good Pharmacy Practice (GPP) is an international standard followed by pharmacies in all developed countries of the world. It is a set of rules designed to ensure the appropriate quality of pharmaceutical services provided by pharmacists to the public, and should cover all issues and aspects of the daily activities of pharmacies.*

Keywords: *standard, GPP, good pharmacy practice, standard operating procedures, pharmaceutical activity.*

Introduction. The standard of good pharmacy practice is designed to ensure the appropriate quality of pharmaceutical services provided by pharmacists to the public and should cover all issues and aspects of the daily activities of pharmacies.

Purpose of the study: to examine the relevance of the implementation of the international standard GPP in the Republic of Uzbekistan and to investigate the number of pharmacies that have received a certificate of compliance with the GPP standard.

Methods and techniques: study of indicators according to the GPP standard on the basis of observation and comparison methods according to the data of “State Unitary Enterprise ”Center of Good Practices“ of the Agency for Development of Pharmaceutical Industry” and evaluation of positive changes in the activities of pharmacy institutions, namely in the retail pharmacy PE “Nargizfarm”.

Results: According to the latest data, 5838 pharmacies out of the total number of pharmacies (12695) received the international GPP certificate, which is 45.9% of all pharmacies in the country. It should be noted that according to Presidential Decree No. UP-20 “On additional measures to regulate the pharmaceutical industry” of January 23, 2024, the deadline for obtaining a GPP certificate is January 1, 2025 for chain pharmacies engaged in retail sales of pharmaceutical products and January 1, 2026 for other pharmacies.

SOP (Standard Operating Procedures) is a set of all the rules related to pharmacy operations. It is kept in the pharmacy as a template for all cases that may arise during operation. For convenience, the SOPs are coded with an identification code (e.g. SOP-501, where SOP is a standard operating procedure, 5 is the corresponding process (11 in total), 01 is the number of the document in the process).

Each document is developed by the pharmacy manager and approved by the director. After, each pharmacy employee must be trained on these documents, where the pharmacy manager trains the quality system for the employees.

This article will detail all of the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) of Nargizfarm, a GPP-compliant private retail pharmacy.

The descriptions of each of the SOPs will be listed below in order.

SOP-1XX - Quality Management.

SOP-101 describes a change management system to ensure that product quality is not jeopardized when changes are made.

SOP-102 establishes the procedure for actions to minimize and/or eliminate deviations and their possible consequences (returns, product recalls, etc.) that occur in any activity that may affect the quality of medicinal products (hereinafter - medicinal products) and medical devices (hereinafter - medical devices). Deviation (event) - A departure from approved procedures, instructions, standards, processes or parameters that affects or may affect the quality of a product. However, it is important to remember that “Deviation” does not mean “non-compliance” or “failure to meet a requirement”.

SOP-103 - governs the procedure for corrective and preventive actions to correct a nonconformance and its cause in the organization's operations. Corrective action - an action taken to eliminate the cause of a detected deviation/nonconformity or other undesirable situation. Preventive action - action taken to eliminate the cause of a potential deviation/nonconformity and prevent the occurrence or recurrence of a deviation/nonconformity or other potentially undesirable situation.

SOP-104 establishes and describes the procedure for review of the quality management system by the top management of the organization. The analysis by the top management is conducted to ensure continuous monitoring of the GPP functioning and to make timely and adequate decisions on correcting and improving the activities of the organization.

SOP-105 establishes and describes methods for managing risks affecting the quality of medicinal products and medical devices in order to protect patient health. FMEA (Failure modes and effects analysis) - Failure modes and effects analysis. An analysis method used in quality management to identify potential defects (nonconformities) and their causes in a product, process or service. It is used to identify problems before they manifest themselves and affect the customer.

SOP-2XX- Personnel Management

SOP-201 describes the procedure for establishing a staff of sufficient qualified personnel to perform all tasks, approving and controlling changes to it, namely designation of a GPP responsible person, planning and selection of human resources, and hiring of employees.

SOP-202 defines the procedure for training of pharmacy staff, which is conducted to establish and maintain the required level of competence and to evaluate the effectiveness of training. There are several types of training: initial training (before starting work); periodic training (in the course of work); emergency training (in case of changes, deviations and identification of discrepancies). And also types of training: with the involvement of internal training trainers (internal training); with the involvement of external trainers (external training). The pharmacy manager undergoes a 144-hour training course in the specialty of pharmacist on the topic “Organization of activities of pharmaceutical enterprises in the implementation of good practice standard” once every 5 years.

SOP-203 describes the rules for ensuring compliance with the sanitary and epidemiologic requirements for pharmacy personnel.

1. Pharmacy staff must observe the following personal hygiene rules:

1.1 Employees and visitors must enter the pharmacy only through the door of the receiving area.

1.2 Wear shoe covers from the “Clean shoe covers” garbage can when entering.

1.3 Proceed to the staff room.

1.4 Remove outerwear and shoes without removing the shoe covers, place in the coat closet labeled for outerwear.

1.5 From the closet labeled “Overalls”, put on special shoes, then overalls.

1.6 Proceed to work only after washing hands and changing into special clothing (medical gown and special shoes).

1.7 Overalls and outerwear are stored in the staff room in separate cabinets.

1.8 Before visiting the toilet, remove overalls, and after visiting the toilet, wash hands thoroughly with soap and disinfect;

1.9 Do not go outside the pharmacy in overalls.

1.10 It is forbidden to keep personal items, except for handkerchiefs, at workplaces and in the pockets of gowns.

1.11 If it is necessary to go out in special footwear to the client part of the sales area (for placement of goods, cleaning), put shoe covers on the special footwear. After the work is done, remove the shoe covers and throw them in the garbage can labeled “Dirty shoe covers”.

1.12 At the end of work, all pharmacy staff members change their overalls and footwear in the staff room. They leave them in the appropriately labeled wardrobe closet.

1.15 When exiting the pharmacy through the reception door, remove from the street.

1.16 Employees must have a corporate uniform: medical gown and pants, neatly gathered hair. Covered girls have a white handkerchief tucked inside the robe. Not bright makeup, light tone of nail polish on hands.

SOP-3XX - premises management

SOP-301 defines the requirements, methods of control and procedures for organizing the admission of pharmacy employees and visitors to the pharmacy and describes the pharmacy premises. Inspectors of the State Unitary Enterprise “Center of Good Practices” of the Agency for Development of Pharmaceutical Industry under the Ministry of Health of RUz; permanently employed staff; temporarily present legal entities (clients, service providers, auditors, inspectors) can be admitted to the pharmacy.

Pharmacy premises and provision of access to them:

1. Control of entrances (exits) to the pharmacy premises (areas):

1.1 Doors to the sales area serve for customers to enter (exit) the pharmacy;

1.2 The door to the goods receiving area is used for loading and unloading of the cargo vehicle for further goods receiving and shipment; entrance and exit of pharmacy employees and visitors.

2. Pharmacy staff, customers and supervisors in the presence of an attendant have access to the sales floor from the entrance to the partition. When entering from the sales floor to the work area (and when entering through the door in the receiving area), everyone must wear clean shoe covers by taking them from the garbage can marked “clean shoe covers” and when leaving, remove dirty shoe covers and put them in the garbage can marked “dirty shoe covers”.

3. The pharmacy manager or designated staff member has access to the receiving and shipping area.

4. The pharmacy manager, or designated pharmacy staff member, has access to the warehouse.

5. The staff room is accessible to all pharmacy staff for the purpose of changing clothes, eating, using the bathroom, and maintaining hygiene.

6. Refrigerators (the pharmacy should have at least 2 refrigerators: one with a temperature range of +2 - +8°C and the other with a temperature range of +8 - +15°C) are accessible by the pharmacy manager or a designated pharmacy staff member.

7. The janitor has access to the inventory storage area.

8. The “Marriage Zone”, which is a closed area, is accessible exclusively by the pharmacy manager.

9. The “Stocking Area” is accessible by the pharmacy manager or a designated pharmacy staff member.

10. The “Quarantine Area” is accessible exclusively by the pharmacy manager.

11. The “Supplier Return Area” is accessible by the pharmacy manager or a designated pharmacy staff member.

All doors and areas shall be used strictly for their intended purpose and shall be locked (opened) by the pharmacy manager or in his/her absence by a designated pharmacy staff member.

Keys shall be kept by the pharmacy manager, or in his/her absence by his/her designated employee, and spare keys shall be kept by the director.

SOP-303 describes the cleaning of premises and maintenance of equipment aimed at the destruction of microorganisms, fungi and other pathogens, as well as the conditions for their reproduction.

Wet cleaning of premises is performed daily, as needed, but at least twice a day, in all rooms of the pharmacy, special attention is paid to disinfection of door handles and windows, pharmacists' workplaces and showcases. General cleaning is carried out at least once a month. Cleaning of the premises shall be carried out in compliance with the following rules.

1. All premises of pharmacies shall be subjected to wet cleaning with the use of special and disinfectants - 0.5% chlorine solution, and in the period of unfavorable epidemiological situation (increased incidence (influenza) with the use of concentrated disinfectants.

2 Window frames, glasses and the spaces between them are washed with hot water and soap or other means at least once a week in the warm season and at least once a month in the cold season. At the same time, windows are washed outside only on warm days or during the thaw in winter.

3. Cabinets for storage of medicines and medical supplies are cleaned as needed, but at least once a week. Drug cabinets and the cash register area are cleaned by pharmacy staff.

4. At least twice a week, the top of the cabinets must be dusted by pharmacy staff.

5. Clean batteries in all areas of the pharmacy once a week.

6. Hand washing sinks and sanitary facilities are cleaned and sanitized daily.

7. Display cabinet doors are wiped down with special detergents at least twice a week

8. Entrance doors to the pharmacy are washed with special detergents daily at least once a day.

9. The corners and ceilings of the premises and exterior walls and pharmacy signage shall be checked daily to ensure there are no cobwebs and cleaned if present.

10. Floors are washed at least twice per shift, and walls and interior doors inside the pharmacy at least once a week, using disinfectants. Ceilings are dusted once a month with damp cloths.

11. Garbage and waste products are collected in a specialized container with a drive lid and taken to a designated place at least once a shift.

12. Wet cleaning with disinfectant once a month is also subjected to cabinets where personal belongings and work clothes of employees are stored.

13. Refrigerators are cleaned once a week.

It is obligatory for the cleaner to fill in the “Logbook of cleaning in the pharmacy premises” immediately after disinfection procedures; it is not allowed to fill in the columns several days in advance.

SOP-304 describes the procedure of preparing the pharmacy for work for comfortable customer service, compliance with corporate requirements:

Step-by-step action of a pharmacy employee at the beginning of work:

1.1. Change into the corporate uniform; change shoes and wash hands with soap and water.

1.2. Perform wet cleaning of shelves, display cases and cash register area.

1.3. Accept the work of the janitor responsible for cleaning, check the pharmacy for cleanliness with a signature in the “Journal of control of cleaning of the premises and equipment of the pharmacy”.

1.4. Check electrical appliances for good working order.

1.5 Quartzing of the premises for 15 minutes in the absence of employees and visitors (before the start of trade and at the end of the working day, or during the day if possible), record in the “Quartzing log”.

1.6. Turn on the work computer and open the shift and turn on the terminals.

1.7. Supplement the cash register area with missing goods, check the sales area for fullness of goods on the shelves and, if necessary, fill with the necessary goods. 1.8.

1.8 Check the landline phone is in good working order and if the phone is not working, submit a repair request to the Director.

1.9. Start working in the pharmacy program, check all the functions of the program, make entries if necessary (defects, assortment, etc.).

SOP-305 describes the program for confirmation of constant compliance with temperature regimes in the operated storage areas, as well as establishes the sequence of actions in case of parameters exceeding the established limits: in each room (area) for storage of medicines and medical devices it is necessary to control the temperature and relative humidity of the air, which should be registered at least once a day in the “Logbook of temperature and relative humidity of the air”, the temperature in the refrigeration equipment is registered at least once a day in the “Logbook of temperature and relative humidity of the air”. On non-working days it is allowed not to carry out control, but not more than one day. If any deviations are detected, the pharmacist shall immediately notify the pharmacy manager.

SOP-306 describes the organization of pest control aimed at preventing the possibility of rodents and insects entering the pharmacy premises and timely detection and extermination of rodents and insects: pharmacy employees monitor sharp temperature changes and condensation in the premises, which forms the habitat for insects and other pests, and monitor and record climatic conditions.

SOP-4XX - equipment management

SOP-401 describes the actions of pharmacy staff in incident management, incident elimination and control of incident elimination within the infrastructure. The primary purpose of

these activities is to maintain temperature conditions in the pharmacy's storage areas for proper storage conditions, prevent accidents, and keep equipment in working order.

SOP-402 describes the verification process for determining and controlling the suitability of measuring instruments. The requirements of this procedure are mandatory for equipment (thermohygrometers) used to control or monitor the storage conditions of medicinal products. It is prohibited to use instruments that have not been verified. thermohygrometers are used for monitoring storage conditions. They must have a passport, manufacturer's certificate of verification and operation manual and must be registered in the state register of Republic of Uzbekistan.

SOP-5XX - Document Management

SOP-501 defines the procedure, methods of control and establishment of requirements in order to ensure the correct sequence of document and records management activities. When documents are implemented, if they are in use and current, they should be stamped "Original" on each page of the SOP. If the document has lost relevance, they should be kept in a separate folder and should be stamped "Archive" where they should be kept for five years.

SOP-6XX - Procurement Management

SOP-601 describes the procedure of supplier evaluation and procurement of goods in accordance with the PPP standard, legal requirements. organization of goods and services. It is allowed to procure medicines and medical devices only from organizations that have a license for pharmaceutical activities for production or distribution of medicines and medical devices issued by the authorized body. Director for evaluation of potential supplier of medicinal products and collects necessary documents:

- registration certificate of the organization;
 - license for pharmaceutical activity;
 - copy of the director's passport;
 - contract;
 - GxP certificate.
- contract with the supplier of medicinal products and medical devices signed by the director.

SOP-7XX - Processing of goods in the pharmacy

SOP-701 defines the procedure and methods of control over acceptance of medicines and medical devices into the pharmacy and establishment of requirements to the organization of work of the pharmacy personnel in order to ensure correct sequence of actions and quality processing of goods. When goods are delivered from the supplier, the director checks the information on payment for the goods in the system during the working day, coordinates with the supplier the date and time of receipt of goods to the pharmacy warehouse.

The pharmacist prepares the receiving area for unloading, it should be completely free, accepts shipping documents from the driver.

If there are any deviations or suspicions of improper storage of goods during transportation, mixing of goods with other products, the goods are not accepted for unloading. Then the goods are taken to the pharmacy, where the pharmacist unloads the goods, stacks them on a pallet, cleans the transportation units (pallets, boxes), then accepts the goods in fact, comparing the data with the shipping documentation In case of violation of the group package, opens it and inspects each consumer package and fixes the identified discrepancies:

- Spoilage;
- Re-sorting;
- Shortage and transfers the shipping documentation with the package of documents for delivery to the pharmacy manager, further places the accepted goods on the shelves of the rack labeled “Warehouse placement area” and fixes the data on the arrival, date.

In case of discrepancy in the quality or quantity of the goods (in the declared document), the pharmacy manager: damaged goods (spoilage) - move them to the “Defect Zone”, and re-sorting, shortages - move them to the “Quarantine Zone”.

SOP-702 SOP is intended for taking measures aimed at preventing scattering, violation of package integrity, contamination and confusion of medicinal products for all pharmacy staff during physical movement of medicinal products (loading, unloading, storage, placement): goods in group packaging are moved manually, when moving goods in group packaging it is necessary to pay attention that the package is closed, then it is necessary to stack medicinal products and medical devices in consumer packaging in shelf boxes or cardboard boxes (hereinafter - box). When stacking the goods in the crate, the packaging should not protrude over the sides. This SOP also describes manipulation marks (marks on the package that indicate how to handle the package and the goods packed in it). In order to prevent spillage, package integrity, and contamination, it is necessary to follow the rules of arrangement of medicinal products and medical devices on the pallet. Also, it is strictly prohibited to place medicinal products and medical devices on the floor.

The SOP-703 methodically describes the process of the removal of foreign materials (i.e. pallets, which are made of wood or plastic, and boxes) from the process of the removal of foreign materials and items intended for reuse. The purification process can be categorised into two distinct types:

- dry cleaning (applied to all types of paper and fabric);
- wet cleaning (applied exclusively to plastic-backed paper and fabric).

It is important to note that the cleaning of the surface of the items being cleaned is not recommended. In the event of the identification of soiling in the form of greasy patches or other types of soiling, the items in question should be transferred to the area designated for cleaning.

The SOP-704 standardises the process of cleaning the air and dust, and the materials used for this purpose. Furthermore, it standardises the verification of the absence of visible damage that may have occurred during the process of transferring the items between the storage facility and the pharmacy.

Results and discussion. The distribution of both medicine and medical products is conducted within the parameters of storage conditions specified in the consumer packaging. The placement of medicine and medical products in group packaging is to be conducted on shelves and under-trays, and their removal from a package without a tray is strictly prohibited.

The pharmacist must conduct a visual examination of the item to verify the condition of the product, noting any discrepancies that may be evident. The goods are to be stored on shelves according to their shelf life. Goods with a shorter shelf life are to be stored in the deeper shelves, and those with a longer shelf life are to be stored closer to the front.

In the initial phase of storage, goods with temperature ranges of +2 to +8 °C and +8 to +15 °C are to be stored in refrigerators with corresponding temperature ranges.

The primary objective of SOP-705 is to establish the requirements for the storage of medicinal substances, including those with medicinal purposes and pharmaceutical efficacy. It is

imperative that pharmaceuticals are stored in a manner that considers their physical and chemical properties within the parameters of the following conditions: It is imperative to ensure that these materials are stored in conditions that preserve their physical properties, moisture content, and resistance to external influences. The storage areas must be protected from the direct effects of solar radiation (e.g. heat, fading, discolouration).

The tablets must be stored in a location that is protected from direct sunlight and moisture. The parapharmaceutical product must be stored in a compartment of the vehicle that is protected from direct sunlight. This compartment should be located in the boot. The pharmaceutical product should be stored in the compartment according to the recommended dosage.

It is imperative to note that the storage of products in the shipping container (box, carton, or equivalent) is strictly prohibited. It is imperative to store the tablets in a location that is protected from direct sunlight and moisture. The pharmaceutical products must be stored in a specialised container, such as a box or a container, and the containers should be labelled according to the intended usage. In the event that the tablets are to be stored in a household cupboard, it is essential to ensure that the cupboard is dry and well-ventilated. It is imperative to ensure the maintenance of sterility in pharmaceutical products during the storage and transportation of goods. This involves the careful handling of products in the absence of direct sunlight, and the utilisation of appropriate containers or packaging materials to ensure the protection of the products from moisture. Furthermore, the storage of products in a manner that allows for effective ventilation is essential to maintain their integrity and quality. Additionally, the storage of products in larger containers should be practised, with the necessary precautions taken to prevent the contamination of the products by moisture or humidity. It is imperative to ensure the maintenance of sterility in the pharmaceutical compounding process, whilst ensuring the integrity of the packaging material is maintained. The storage of medical devices made of resin (e.g. greases, tubes, syringes, and ointments) in containers with high-temperature-resistant materials (e.g. waxes, wax esters, and fatty acids) is recommended.

The storage of nitroglycerin in larger volumes is also recommended, as is the storage of glycerin and water together, as well as the storage of sterility-preserving materials in vials. It is imperative to consider the following aspects:

- The storage of sterile materials (goggles, tubes, syringes, capsules) in proximity to materials that can absorb fat (oils, fats, and waxes).

The SOP-8XX- management system is responsible for the reduction of non-compliant products.

The SOP-801 establishes the framework for the reduction of non-compliant products. The latter is defined as a non-standard product, and is defined in the context of a contract with the State Committee for Protection of the Environment and the Sanitation and Epidemiology Centre.

The SOP-9XX The procedure for the sale of medicines and medical devices from a pharmacy

The SOP-901 protocol delineates the stipulations for the provision of pharmaceuticals and medical devices for personal use: The sale of medicinal products is permitted to individuals who possess a pharmaceutical degree and are engaged in retail sales. The SOP-901 protocol stipulates the terms and conditions for the sale of pharmaceuticals from pharmacies to customers, including the sale of pharmaceuticals for specific medical purposes, as well as the sale of pharmaceuticals that are imported and the sale of pharmaceuticals that are purchased from domestic manufacturers.

The sale of medical products and equipment is subject to a maximum retail price, which is determined by the number of intermediaries involved in the supply chain. The sale of medical products and services is only permitted to individuals who have a professional pharmaceutical degree and who are registered with the relevant authorities. The sale of medical products and services is allowed only to the extent of 20% of the market price. The sale of medical products and services that require mandatory certification is prohibited. The importation of goods is subject to customs duties, which are calculated based on the number of intermediaries involved in the supply chain. The amount of these duties is less than 20% of the retail price, and does not include additional costs for goods that are not subject to mandatory certification or verification. This includes items that are not registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as those that are not subject to compulsory certification.

The SOP-902 outlines the procedure for the sale of medical products in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are subject to prescription. The procurement of pharmaceuticals is subject to the prescription of a medical practitioner, as stipulated in the relevant legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In the event of an order being placed for a prescription, the pharmacist enters the customer's details into the 'Journal of prescription records', fills the prescription, and issues the customer with the required documentation. The prescription is to be completed by the pharmacist, who is also responsible for ensuring that the correct name, dosage, quantity, and the pharmacist's details are entered. The prescription is then stamped 'for prescriptions', and the pharmacist issues the prescription to the patient. In the event that a prescription is not filled out correctly by the physician, the pharmacist must stamp it 'Prescription invalid' and send an informative letter to the physician with the details. These procedures are documented in the " Journal of incorrectly written prescriptions ". The prescription is valid for a period of three months, after which it is subject to renewal.

The SOP-10XX is a document that details the quality standards for the medicine

The SOP-1001 is a record of the work that has been carried out with the quality standards for the medicine. It also includes the medical standards that have been established. The pharmacist, during the process of examining the medical history of the patient, examines the medical history of the patient and immediately notifies the supervising physician. In addition, the pharmacist will provide the relevant centre with a map of all the actions that are not desired, and will also inform the responsible person at the centre without delay. The director will provide the supplier with a written statement. He then assesses the supplier's performance in terms of the most recent prescriptions, and provides the manager with the necessary information. The latter is then passed on to the supervising physician. The subsequent actions are with the purchaser, or the purchaser's agent, or the purchaser's agent, or the purchaser's agent.

The SOP-1002 protocol stipulates the actions to be taken by the pharmaceutical establishment in the event of the occurrence of a product that exhibits signs of falsification or adulteration. Furthermore, SOP-1002 stipulates the protocol to be followed in the event of the occurrence of a pharmaceutical product with signs of falsification or adulteration, as well as the measures to be taken to prevent the dissemination of such products to the pharmacy sector. In this context, the extent and reliability of the measures taken to address these issues are of paramount importance. In the event of suspicion or identification of falsified or counterfeit medicine, In such

cases, the products in question are to be isolated in a "zone of danger" and the customer is to be informed of the need for further action.

The SOP-11XX is a self-inspection.

The SOP-1101 is a standard that sets out the requirements for GPP and the actions of those who are responsible for its implementation and the actions of those who are responsible for its oversight and improvement.

The self-inspection process involves the assessment of the performance of the pharmacy by a person who is not employed by the pharmacy, in order to determine compliance with the requirements of the GPP. The objective of the self-inspection is to verify the performance of the GPP, as well as the actions of the relevant actors. The objective of the self-inspection process is to assess the effectiveness of the management system in place. The objective of self-inspection is to evaluate the performance of the pharmacy in relation to the established standards and guidelines for its activities, as defined by the relevant authorities and standards bodies. The process involves the identification of areas that require improvement and the determination of the mechanisms for achieving these improvements.

Conclusions. The implementation of the GPP standard allows to significantly improve the quality of pharmaceutical services, providing the population with only high-quality medicines. According to the requirements of this standard, in particular, pharmacies must strictly monitor the temperature regime in the pharmacy, the humidity level, ensuring optimal values for these indications and record changes to prevent incorrect storage of medicines, which is the main factor affecting the quality of products. Also, this standard describes in detail the procedure for actions upon detection or suspicion of poor quality of products, falsification and the occurrence of complaints and claims for unwanted side effects from the patient, which was previously insufficiently regulated.

The implementation of the standard will enable pharmacies to describe in detail the procedure for all actions within the pharmaceutical enterprise by creating appropriate SOPs (standard operating procedures), where all actions and rules are spelled out in detail (quality management, requirements for personnel, premises, equipment, documentation, the procedure for purchasing, processing, destruction, sale of medicines, quality claims management and the procedure for conducting an internal audit). The implementation of the standard will ultimately lead to increased efficiency of the pharmacy organization, providing the population with exclusively high-quality medicines due to strict control by regulatory authorities.

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